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OPTIMIZING DESIGN RESEARCH COURSES FOR MASTER STUDENTS IN GERMANY WITH THE SECI MODEL

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes the development of a master level research course for German Industrial Design students that required the prototyping and testing of models just as in design practice. The aim of the course is to enable students to face the demand for new knowledge and methods needed for future decision-making. In order to optimize content and structures for participant's motivation and learning the course was restructured following the SECI Model for knowledge management. This led to a dramatic increase in the overall student's achievements and satisfaction as reflected in questionnaires and student's performance.

Keywords: Industrial Design, Design Research Education, SECI model

INTRODUCTION

Although the subject of Design Research is still being established in Germany (ROMERO-TEJEDOR & JONAS 2010) an increasing number of designers are interested in a more scientific approach and programs to the subject. This is evidenced by the growing number of doctoral research in the subject of design and the rising number of members in Design Research Organizations such as the DGTF.

In addition the introduction of the Bologna-system changed the overall German educational structures including the design study paths. As a result Design Research became part of the curriculum of several design Universities. Before that design

theory courses were commonly held alongside the practice-based education and hardly had an influence on product development processes in Germany. But prospective designers will have to face the demand for new knowledge and methods to inform decision-making described by DAVIS (2008). STROUSE & ARNOLD (2009) actually argued "design research will empower designers to have direct and meaningful impact on the world, contributing significantly to the way people live and improving society as a whole."

After their inquiry about the role of Industrial Design in a cooperative research center MELLEES, GINTERS & KUYS (2009) came to the conclusion that „only a balance of prototype, process and reflection can help establish the academic and disciplinary status of design“.

In order to meet these new requirements design theory should directly interfuse design practice. This intention is not generally new. But triggered by the structural changes in recent years it was renamed with design research or design science. This led to the demand for a community of researchers who where educated in design and are able to apply practical experience.

As interdisciplinary communication is a significant task throughout product development processes the described demand for new knowledge and methods

does not only concern designers planning an academic career but all designers.

In most of the disciplines involved in these processes academic reading and writing clearly is a standard requirement even in undergraduate curricula. As the idea of a designer as an artistic genius no longer suits to this day and age methodological knowledge needs to be taught at least within Master's Programs for Designers. The students should already gain experience to choose, apply and refine research methods during university studies. This is clearly a requirement for interdisciplinary collaboration on an equal footing.

This does not seem to be only a problem for Industrial Designers. Regarding Human Computer Interaction ZIMMERMAN, FORLIZZI & EVENSON (2007) had huge struggles to integrate the perspective of design thinking in the collaborative research environment. They declared, "Design has a good foothold in practice but much less impact on the research community".

THE EDUCATIONAL SITUATION

Teaching in a field that is still being defined raises educational questions and is also new for students. Because undergraduate Design curricula mainly focus on the refinement of practice-oriented skills, the majority of the students are not used to academic reading and writing. As a start they need to become aware of the gap in their knowledge. They should learn to distinguish between hands-on data collection and academic design research.

In addition the majority of the lecturers do not have a lot of practical experience with the subject and many Design Professors in Germany were appointed to a professorship based on their practical references - they often did not earn a doctorate themselves.

But this does not seem to be only a German problem but exists in several countries.

Referring to the USA HANINGTON (2010) wrote: "One reason why many design schools do not have explicit instruction in research methods is that there are few design instructors that have the experience or educational qualifications to teach research methodology."

FINDELY (2010) points out that one of the most important steps for PhD candidates in design is "to transform their design questions into research questions" but because of the lack of "the necessary competence to switch from the realm of design questions to the realm of research questions... it is wrong ...to request from PhD candidates that they manage this transformation by themselves." In his opinion this is the task of their supervisors.

Considering the fact that at present many supervisors in Germany are also short on academic design research experience "the necessary intellectual mastery" (FINDELY 2010) needs to be acquired through the prototyping and testing of models. In addition this process has to be supported by guest lectures, critics and suggestions of more experienced co-supervisors. At the beginning of this process this often happens through the involvement of related disciplines well versed in academic research.

As the number of designers who received a PhD rises steadily, applicants for design research education will probably have to demonstrate academic experience, in the future. Hopefully the correlation of research and practice oriented design education will then be interlinked more systematically. And it may be helpful when supervisors teaching research methodology are using the same domain-specific terminology. An alliance of practical and methodological oriented designers in education may also help design research to gain recognition.

THE EDUCATIONAL CONCEPT

The exemplified Masters Program - offered since 2008 - includes a cross-disciplinary approach; it does not build on Bachelor in Industrial Design, but accepts suitable students holding a bachelor degree in the areas of design, architecture, mechanical engineering or other design related disciplines. The program's emphasis is on conveying an interdisciplinary understanding of design and design research.

Within the two-year Industrial Design curriculum students participate in two Design Research modules (DR1 and DR2) that are based on each other. The ultimate goal of the course is to encourage self-elaborated design research.

The „generic research skills procedures and methodology“ (NEWBURY) learned should eventually help students to interlink research and practice. These skills are needed within the master thesis and possibly for continuation with a PhD project.

The motive for the evaluation of this course was to work out a procedure to ensure continuous improvement of the quality of teaching. Regarding the demand described in the introduction the main focus was the improvement of participant's intrinsic motivation (DECI & RYAN 2000) and methodological learning. The promotion of intrinsic motivation should ensure that students are getting engaged in the field's advancement, later on.

INTERDISCIPLINARY TEAMS

Educating students with various backgrounds is especially difficult because of multiple - sometimes even competing - logics. WÖLFEL (2010) observed that novice Design students holding a Bachelor Degree in engineering often face problems in activating their knowledge within design processes. In addition to this phenomenon the students have to face the

contradictions between rigorous empirical methods generally applied by engineers and qualitative questions addressed by designers. But if these two very different points of view are systematically combined through a mixed methods approach working processes can become prolific. Inquiries carried out by interdisciplinary student teams are a good chance to learn from each other.

THE RESEARCH DESIGN

The first prototype of the course was developed based on personal teaching experiences and theoretical assumptions on students learning and motivation. The content was based on a literature review.

After the first iteration of both parts of the course (DR1 & DR2) learning outcomes and difficulties students and supervisors had noticed were discussed. The students were asked to make suggestions for improvement. Conclusions drawn from this inquiry led to a set of assumptions about reasonable changes for the second iteration. Therefore students' criticism, suggestions and learning were compared with the supervisor's observations and finally led to the development of an optimized prototype.

Figure 1. Process for the improvement of the master level Design Research course. In this process there are three fields of activity for the lecturer: the gain in personal experience, the teaching process and the monitoring and inquiries regarding students motivation and learning.

After the second iteration learning outcomes and difficulties were discussed again. Then the documented processes of both iterations of the course were compared to monitor if the changes had a positive effect on students learning and motivation. Findings led to the development of the third prototype, which is currently tested for further improvements. The research design is illustrated in figure 1.

The illustrated process consists of three interdependent fields of activity for the lecturer - the gain in experience and knowledge, the teaching process (including coordination, supervision and feedback) and the monitoring and inquiries to gain insights for further developments.

EVALUATION PROCESS

First the evaluation process was run through with a control group (1st prototype of the course) the following year the same process was run through by the treatment group (2nd prototype of the course). In order to improve quality of teaching the level of motivation, the learning process and the results of the two groups were measured and compared as shown in figure 2.

CURRICULUM DEVELOPMENT

FIRST PROTOTYPE

To work out ideal content and structures for participant’s motivation and learning in spite of the difficulties described above, the course was presented as an experimental prototype at the first iteration.

Figure 2. Evaluation process in order to improve quality of teaching

The students were advised that it was a chance for them to take part in the development process.

Having NEWBURY’s statement in mind that „It is the practice of research in art and design that will ultimately be important“, the first prototype consisted of a theoretical introduction followed by two experimental studies carried out by the students. The only predefined aspect was to apply an approach according to FRAYLING (1993). The course mainly focused on the realization of very small self-elaborated research projects.

Throughout the first iteration it became obvious that there was an immense schism between students tacit and explicit knowledge (POLANYI).

That was why the intention of the course was newly formulated:

- It should enable students to transfer their gained tacit knowledge to explicit knowledge.
- Students should apply explicit knowledge within self-elaborated projects to acquired additional tacit knowledge.
- Finally gained insights should be communicated to fellow students and supervisors.

THE SECI MODEL

The SECI Model (NONAKA & TAKEUCHI 1995) for knowledge management processes served as an inspiration for the development of the second prototype of the course. The theoretical framework is based upon the two forms of knowledge described before and is aimed at continuous knowledge creation through non-stop individual and organizational self-renewal. A simple illustration based on the SECI Model is shown in table 1.

The process illustrated by the SECI Model is divided into four recurring modes of knowledge conversion: Socialization (apprenticeship), Externalization (dialogue to develop group’s mental model), Combination (newly created concepts with existing knowledge) and Internalization (individuals producing or using concepts). The Model takes the form of a spiral to illustrate its dynamic never-ending nature.

tacit/tacit	tacit / explicit	explicit/explicit	explicit / tacit
Socialization	Externalization	Combination	Internalization
(observation, imitation exercises, discussions)	(application & communication of tacit knowledge)	(conception or product development, design practice)	(individual experience, knowing)

Table 1. Linear illustration of the process based on the SECI Model (NONAKA & TAKEUCHI) in comparison to the course structure. Lines from top to bottom: knowledge forms, steps of the SECI model, applied teaching structures.

SECOND PROTOTYPE

Thus the second iteration of the course had to be restructured. A comparison of structure and tasks of the first and second prototype is shown in figure 3. To procure knowledge about the limitations of research the learning process has been divided into four steps - according to the SECI Model. In the first step limitations were explained with a simple Graphic (figure 3) and a citation from ECO that says the aim of your inquiry should be to become the highest living authority to this very special issue. In addition research examples were discussed (Socialization to develop the group’s mental models).

Figure 3. Graphic used in the Socialization process to explain the limitation of research to the students

The second step was to work out self-elaborated research topics (Externalization). In the third step this was supported by discussions and suggestions regarding feasibility (Combination). The last step was to carry out the planned studies (Internalization).

Several exercises like quantitative self-experiments or qualitative interviews had been prepared to help students learn to distinguish between design questions and research questions (FINDELY). They should gain a feeling for the complexity of academic research and should learn from mistakes that appear if the research process was not planned and tested well enough. Therefore all participants primarily had to work on predefined topics with predefined methods and questionnaires in DR1.

In addition although everybody had to use the same questionnaire the inquiries had been carried out in different manners thus some findings were not representative. Before the comparison of the collected data some of the students have not been aware of this risk. Working with predefined topics and methods in DR1 was planned as a motivational tool for DR2, too.

Another challenge for DR2 students at the second iteration of the course was to communicate their self-elaborated research

objectives and methods clearly and easy to understand (Externalization). One or two design students who were participating in DR1 supported the DR2 student's in carrying out their self-elaborated inquiries. In return they could assign several tasks to the DR1 students and it was possible to discuss their concepts with them (Socialization). The DR1 students had received a theoretical introduction before the team matching.

MONITORING OF LEARNING OUTCOMES

At the end of the cooperation described above the students who participated in DR1 and DR2 were asked to evaluate the four project phases regarding the behavior of all group-members (including self assessment). The evaluation covered the following aspects:

- Efficiency of Teamwork
- Responsibility assignment
- Motivation of group members
- Commitment of group members

In consideration of the same aspects the difficulties addressed and the groups progress were documented and evaluated by the lecturer during weekly monitoring sessions.

The final presentations and documentations of the student projects were evaluated considering the following criteria:

1st Prototype		2nd Prototype	
1st term	2nd term	1st term	2nd term
Introduction: What is Design Research ? Why should Designer do Research? Christopher Frayling's 3 DR approaches & Literature recommendations	DR2 / task predefined: - arbitrary: research approach topic & object of investigation selection criteria for test persons methods for research and evaluation project conditions: individual work self elaborated research weekly counselling session (optional)	Introduction: What is Design Research ? Why should Designer do Research? Christopher Frayling's 3 DR approaches & Literature recommendations	Library introduction - compulsory „How to cite / literature research“ <u>Examples & creative writing workshop</u>
Library introduction - optional DR1 / task predefined: one of Fraylings approaches arbitrary: topic & object of investigation selection criteria for test persons methods for research and evaluation project conditions: groups of 3 - 4 students self elaborated research weekly counselling session		<u>Exercises:</u> perception & inquiry DR1 / task predefined: topics & objects of investigation selection criteria for test persons methods for research and evaluation research approach arbitrary: - project conditions: all participants are research assistants weekly progress monitoring	DR2 / task predefined: - arbitrary: - topic & object of investigation - selection criteria for test persons - methods for research and evaluation - research approach project conditions individual work, 1-2 assisting students self elaborated research weekly counselling session

Figure 4. The two prototypes of the course in comparison. Differences in structure and tasks are underlined.

- Relevance of selected topics
- Methods applied for inquiry and analysis
- Clarity of communicated findings
- Insights gained in the course
- Realistic self-assessment

THE RESULTS

Due to the changes in the course structure and differences in team constellation a quantitative comparison of the data did not seem to be reasonable. A qualitative comparison and a description of general tendencies and peculiarities were found to be more appropriate.

STUDENT RESPONSES FIRST ITERATION

After the first iteration of DR1 students described their difficulties working with the mandatory literature on their own and suggested to gather the theoretical framework together through varying methods (presentations, reviews, discussion and exercises) and voted for more theory divided in smaller parts throughout the overall working process. They were especially interested in qualitative not quantitative research (less rigor more relevance) and asked for more discussions with guests (experts) from other disciplines.

LEARNING OUTCOMES FIRST ITERATION

After the first iteration of DR2 the author noticed that the quality of the final presentations and documentations differed a lot and there seemed to be coherence with student's personal environment or prior experiences. The students with the best learning outcomes had an educational background in engineering or ergonomics or had an external personal coach. The overall learning outcomes and insights students gained in the course were not satisfying and led to the conclusion that changes in the educational concept were required. The course structure should assure

effective learning for both - participants with or without experience or external coaching.

Students without methodological research experience generally had huge difficulties to apply the theoretical knowledge to the conception of an operational model for their work (Externalization). Regarding the SECI Model these problems were to be expected. The Externalization process should not be started before the Socialization process was finished. If the Externalization process does not function it is helpful to repeat the Socialization process with different methods.

This insight brings us back to the lecturer's lack of experience mentioned in the introduction. Practical examples from expert researchers are one possibility to bridge this lack of experience.

REASONABLE CHANGES AFTER FIRST ITERATION

Central aspects that needed to be considered for the improvement of the course were:

- Improvement of the learning process inspired by the SECI model
- Integration of creative writing workshops and a library introduction to respond to designer's lack of reading and writing skills (Socialization)
- Supervision of experiments with empirical methods in a controlled context to procure an operational understanding of what constitutes research (Socialization & Externalization)
- Using visual methods to work out research objectives in teamwork (Combination)
- A greater focus on interdisciplinary exchange between designers & engineers (Combination & Socialization)

- Guidance of different Socialization processes for Students with different educational backgrounds
- Application of motivational tools

STUDENT RESPONSES SECOND ITERATION

According to the plan students addressed their wish to undertake research on self-elaborated topics after the second iteration of DR1. There, they had to work with predefined topics and methods and complained about the amount of work referring to the transliteration of qualitative Interviews (despite that they voted it to be the most interesting method). In addition they mentioned that they had trouble to draw relevant conclusions working with quantitative data. Throughout the process students critique increased the more the structure of the research was pre-defined. At the end, when they were told that it was one of the central aims to provoke this kind of critique they apparently noticed the need to reconsider their point of view. Later on they concluded that everyone had learned a lot.

After the second iteration of DR2 the student's feedback was quite positive, all of them were content with their own works and found the final presentations of their fellow students to be interesting and inspiring. The only suggestion for improvement was more collaborative interpretation and analysis of published texts to reinforce methodological and theoretical inspiration (Socialization & Combination).

LEARNING OUTCOMES SECOND ITERATION

As was to be expected - with respect to intrinsic motivation (BAETZ et al. 2009) - working with predefined topics and methods had a negative effect for student's motivation at first but finally lead to profound questions and empathic discussions. Further on the increase of self-determination from DR1 to DR2 obviously

had a positive effect on student's motivation.

Mentoring novice Design Research students turned out to be difficult and exhausting but on the other hand most of the DR2 students described the working processes of their teams as inspiring and questions as well as critiques of the DR1 student's led to a greater motivation.

Further conclusions drawn from the evaluation of the second prototype were:

- The awareness of the personal research scope rises faster when students are primarily involved as research assistants in predefined projects.
- Working (only) as assistants raises student's motivational problems and skepticism but may encourage their motivation for an arbitrary topic.
- Predefined experiments help to deal with learning barriers (Socialization) because it is easier for novice design researchers to take up a stance on predefined subjects than on their own projects (empathy).
- Tutoring fosters student's awareness of the know-how they already acquired.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Throughout the overall observation students with an engineering background have shown considerably more timidity to qualitative experiment and initial skepticism. They preferred to come back to well-known methods and paradigms.

Students with a design background didn't hesitate to carry out probes and showed much more empathy. Their experiments had positive (raising motivation) as well as negative (not representative) effects.

The higher the level of Socialization in a specific field the higher the student's

motivation to work it out in detail. The lower the level of Socialization in a specific field the harder it was to encourage them to undertake their first attempts.

Another example for this is:

At the beginning Design students - who had less reading and writing skills - did not refer to other people's work and loved to start from the very beginning. They tended to work without acquiring available basic knowledge. They often failed to work out the details and to show the references that led them to their theoretical framework. Because of their educational background (Socialization) they were used to start from zero and to develop concepts based on their implicit knowledge only. In addition they were used to a creative contest and hesitated to show intermediate concepts to their fellow students.

Engineering students were used to academic reading and writing but had trouble to work out the detailed job definition independently. They were used to receive a clearly structured briefing. In addition they were mainly interested in measuring the value of design.

Design students were generally interested in complex - „wicked problems“ (RITTEL and WEBBER 1973) and wished to improve their ability to explain their job profile. This seems only logical as these topics are often discussed in Design education.

As mentioned in the introduction FINDELY described a transformation process from design to research questions - this seemed to be the same phenomenon.

At the beginning design students tended to work with statements and were not used to share findings with their peers. They also tended to copy original text without interpretation or reflection and expressed their lack of self-esteem in terms of academic research (lack of Socialization).

If the motivation was high, students generally had problems with decision-making - everything seemed to be quite interesting to them. For these students it was especially difficult to focus on manageable aspects of inquiry.

If motivation was lower they tended to choose the path of least resistance and topics as well as test persons that seemed to be obvious and easy to observe. These decisions seemed to have an additional counterproductive effect on their motivation.

The evaluation of the course has shown that the ideal content and structures for participant's motivation and learning depend on the particular educational background and personal experiences. Special attention has to be paid to the diversity of interpretations. Theoretical content has to be mediated orally as well as visually to ensure an ideal learning process of all participants and it should bring up different points of view.

Using the SECI model as a guideline to improve student's learning processes led to a dramatic increase in the overall student's achievements and satisfaction as reflected in questionnaires and student's performance. The model may generally be a good tool for lecturers to evaluate their teaching methods and content and to look for missing steps in the process if student's achievements are not satisfying.

FUTURE DEVELOPMENTS

As mentioned before the third iteration of the course is currently observed for further improvements. The comparison of the second and third iteration may lead to additional findings and a framework for quantitative measurement of student's learning and motivation.

The ultimate intention of this inquiry and evaluation was to elaborate on some practical insights for supervisors not experienced in design research

methodology. In a next step findings may also serve to work out a general framework for the implementation of the SECI Model process into practical Design Education with the ambition to bring forward the fusion of design research and practice.

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